

ASSESSMENT OF PASSIVE INDOOR ENVIRONMENTAL COMFORT ON MID-RISE OFFICE BUILDINGS IN TROPICAL WET AND DRY CLIMATE OF NIGERIA

BY

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ABSTRACT

The study is an introductory work of passive indoor environmental comfort (PIEC) research, being undertaken on office buildings in Nigeria. Studies have shown that, there is need to reduce the amount of energy consume by the office buildings globally and in Nigeria. Moreover, office buildings in Nigeria have poor indoor environmental comfort, and the few studies conducted on IEC in Nigerian office buildings did not cover all the seasonal changes of climatic conditions experienced in any of its climatic zone. The aim of the study is to investigate the current conditions of the two (2) mid-rise office buildings in Zaria and Kaduna metropolis which are in wet and dry climate of Nigeria. It was achieved by exploring the level of compliance with IEC requirements of office buildings in fulfilling the daylight autonomy (DA), useful daylight illuminance (UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀), spatial daylight autonomy (sDA), operative temperature, relative humidity, and ventilation rate (ach), based on international standards. The google sketch-up 2017 and openstudio simulation tool were used to evaluate the 13 offices in Ahmadu Bello University (ABU) senate building and Nagwamatse house. An exploratory design approach with the quantitative research strategy were employed in the study and the data generated was then analysed using statistical tools such as bar charts and tables. The results show that none of the IEC indicators meet the standard's thresholds of IEC. It has also been observed that, building form, room orientation, window to wall ratio (WWR), openable window to floor area ratio, building heights and roofing materials, influence the daylight and thermal comfort of an office building. The study concludes that, for mid rise office buildings in tropical wet and dry climate of Nigeria to meet the passive IEC requirements based on international standards, there is need to look at their building forms, orientations, WWR, and openable window to floor area ratios.

Keywords: Daylight, Ventilation, Indoor Environmental Comfort, Open-studio, Thermal comfort,

INTRODUCTION

Passive Indoor Environmental Comfort (IEC) is simply a condition of architectural space where the Optimum thermal, natural luminous and natural air quality are maintained. Workers spend an average of 8 hours indoor in their offices daily especially those working in multi storey office buildings. Having IEC is therefore very important component to the occupants as observed by

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Wright, (nd) who concluded that, performance is a function of the three factors acting together: Ability; Motivation; and Opportunity. These are all influenced by comfort as indicated by Heerwagen (1998) & (Nian, Wang, & Zhao, 2017). A number of researches have shown that, thermal comfort, indoor air quality, and daylight, are the main parameters for determining IEC in Office buildings as shown by Huang, Zhu, Ouyang & Cao (2012); Lim, (2013); and Sakellaris, et al (2016).

It has been established that, building sector put away more than 40% of the world's energy (UNEP, 2015) and 50% of the energy in Office buildings are used for Heating Ventilation and Air conditioning HVAC (Bastide, A., et al, 2006). For example, in 1950s, 25% of US's electricity were consumed by building sector and has grown to 40% in the early 1970s and to more than 76% by 2012 (EIA, 2010). Another example is France, whose building sector consumes about 44% of the total energy use per year, from which 70% is used only for the thermal comfort on the dwellers (Butler, 2008). While in African countries such as Nigeria, building sector takes more than 65% of the total energy used in the country (Ahmed, Isa, layande, & Ojosu, 2014). This is because most of the office buildings especially multi-storey buildings depend on mechanical means rather than passive means.

Studies that combined Natural daylight, thermal and Natural Indoor Air Quality (IAQ) in office buildings in Nigeria are fewer in number and the few studies conducted did not reflect the changing climatic conditions experienced in the country. For example, Kadiri, Sells, Ukpomwan, & Salau, (2014) studied indoor environmental quality (IEQ) in multi storey office buildings and its implication on the health and safety of workers: evaluation of Lagos (tropical wet climate) state government administrative buildings in Nigeria, between February to April, 2012 while Ali, Martinson & Al-Maiyah, (2016) studied IEQ of learning environments in Bayero University, Kano (hot semi-arid climate) between 12th to 27th January, 2016. None of the aforementioned studies covered even the full wet or dry season of its climatic zone.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The aim of this study is to investigate the current conditions of the two (2) mid-rise office buildings in Zaria and Kaduna metropolis both in wet and dry climate of Nigeria. The objectives of the study are: to determine the level of compliance with IEC requirements of office buildings in wet and dry

climate of Nigeria in fulfilling the daylight autonomy (DA), useful daylight illuminance (UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀), continuous daylight autonomy (cDA), Spatial daylight autonomy (sDA) based on Architectural Energy Corporation, AEC (2006), Society of Light and Lighting, SLL(2011) requirements; to determine the extent of compliance of operative temperature, relative humidity, and ventilation rate (ach), relative to (American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineer) ANSI/ASHRAE standards. The evaluation studies were undertaken to answer the following:

- i. What is the level of compliance in daylighting requirements of office buildings in Nigeria in fulfilling the DA, sDA, cDA and UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀ performance metrics put forward by AEC and SLL?
- ii. To what extent does the operative temperature and relative humidity comply with ANSI/ASHRAE standard 55, (2017)?
- iii. To what extent does ventilation rate comply with ANSI/ASHRAE standard 62.1, (2016)?

LITERATURE REVIEW

A Mid Rise building in this study, means any building with 4 to 12 floors, as classified by Alcox (2017) and Freedman (2009). The typology of office buildings varies from Engineering, Estate managers to Architecture point of views. Even in Architecture, there are various perspectives to office building classifications which include, Neufert (1980), who classified office buildings based on primary circulation as: Single banked office; and double banked office buildings. Peter (1965) classified office building based on the sizes, as: small office building, with 1858m² floor area; medium office building, with 1856m² to 9290m²; and large office building, with total floor area greater than 9290m². He also classified it based on access and services, as: Slab-type block; and the Core-type plan. In this study, office building is classified based on the position of the building service core, because it influences building IEC as observed by Elotefya, Abdelmagidab, Morghanya, & Ahmed, (2015). Office building in this research is categorized into two: centrally located service core (such as Office of the New Nigeria Publishing Company Nagwamatse house, Kaduna), and eccentrically located service core (Such as Senate Building, ABU Zaria).

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There are many types of comforts, such as relief, ease, and transcendence (Kolcaba, 2010), but ease environmental comfort is what will be the concern of this research, which is the process of assessing comfort needs through environmental factors, such as: thermal; hygienic; visual; auditory; and olfactory comforts. Thermal comfort, indoor air quality (IAQ), and daylight, are the main components in determining passive IEC in office buildings. There are a number of ways to measure these components, but the most effective daylight model is the Climate-Based Daylight Modelling (Salisu, 2013), which this study has adopted for daylighting; while Adaptive model is chosen for measuring thermal comfort as well as IAQ in this study, because, it is most appropriate for passive thermal comfort measurement (ASHRAE 55, 2017).

EnergyPlus, Ecotec, DesignBuilder and OpenStudio are some of the leading energy simulation tools in today's world of building research technology. EnergyPlus is the most prominent and has the capabilities of BLAST and DOE-2, and extensively validated for over 20years (Sousa, date; Crawley, Hand, Kummert, & Griffith, 2005). However, Guglielmetti, Macumber, and Long (2011), noticed that, EnergyPlus and DOE-2 have clear limitations in their daylight simulation algorithms. Their engines cannot accurately model daylight flux transfer into complex spaces, and can model only a limited number of daylight redirection technologies. On the other hand, Crawley, Hand, Kummert, & Griffith, (2005) have observed the limitations of Ecotec in predicting natural ventilation as well as achieving passive thermal comfort. Moreover, DesignBuilder is not fast in analyzing a multiple simulation when compare to OpenStudio. OpenStudio is easier to visualize the building geometry and do some basic editing compared to other 3. Through both PAT and the OpenStudio Analysis Spreadsheet, it increased the proficiency for users to run a large number of simulations. (Long, Ball, Fleming, & Macumber, 2014). Its users can import IDF file, edit surfaces and zones in the file and can set and change default constructions and assign daylighting controls (Rallapalli, 2010). For these reasons, open-studio is chosen for this study.

METHODOLOGY

The study used simulation method to evaluate the passive IEC of the 13 number measured virtual offices of ABU senate building Zaria and Nagwamatse house Kaduna, in google sketch-up 2017 and open-studio simulation tool, after validating the instrument and found it suitable for the

research. An exploratory design approach using quantitative research strategy were employed and a convenience probability sampling technique was used in selecting the buildings. The criteria used in selection of these buildings was based on the difference in their Orientations, and building form. Other selection criteria include: number of storeys (mid-rise buildings); access to buildings; and HVAC system. Data was obtained from 13 offices of those buildings as shown in the table1.

Table 1. Study Population of offices in ABU Senate building and Nagwamatse office building.

S/No.	Building Name	Location	Building Form	Building Orientation	Floor level	Office Tag.	Ownership	
							Public	Private
1	ABU Senate building	Samaru, Zaria	Eccentrically located service core	315 ⁰	1st	Academic Office	1	0
					3 rd	Computer Room	1	0
					4 th	Filing Room	1	0
					5 th	Record Office	1	0
					6 th	Secretary to Human Resources	1	0
					8 th	Office/Store	1	0
					2	New Nigeria News Paper office Building	Nagwamut se House, Kaduna, metropolis	Centrally located service core
2 nd	Estate Surveyors	0	1					
3 rd	MD AA Usman & CO	0	1					
4 th	Mother Care, Gen. Office	0	1					
5 th	Drawing Office	0	1					
6 th	KD Consults	0	1					
8 th	Accounting Office	0	1					

Source: Fieldwork, 2018

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The procedure used in conducting the research is based on the following documents: Daylighting Monitoring Protocols & Procedures for Buildings, 1997; Monitoring Procedures for Assessment of Daylighting Performance of Buildings, 2001 (both published by the International Energy Agency IEA); 2015 International Energy Conservation Code, USA; ASHRAE standards; and Indoor Air Quality Handbook, 2013. Based on those documents the following steps were followed:

- Two office buildings were modelled in google sketch-up (including all properties of materials and ground reflectance) as shown in figure 1, and 2 below.

Figure 1. Simulated IEC of the Offices in Kaduna Nagwamatse house, (1-8th Floors).

Figure 2. Simulated IEC of the Offices in ABU Senate building, Zaria.

Source: Field study, 2018

- In order to simulate IEC components, such as daylight, IAQ and thermal comfort, EnergyPlus weather (EPW) was used as the type of weather file.
- Open-studio as sketch-up plugging was used to set weather files of Zaria and Kaduna from weather Analytic, space types, thermal zones, construction materials and other settings.
- Radiance measure for daylight and open-studio for ventilation and thermal comfort was used, and then simulation button was pressed for the final analysis.

RESULTS AND DATA ANALYSIS

The results of the pilots-evaluation studies with respect to task illuminance measurements, operative temperature, ventilation rate, and relative humidity were presented on table 2 and 3. The

analysis was done based on the benchmarks put forward by professional institutes and other determinants that were discovered in the studies. IESNA (2000) and ASHRAE 90.1, (2010) have recommended the use of 500 lux as illuminance task in office buildings, while ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 55, (2013) recommends a temperature range between 24.3°C to 29.3°C within a humidity of 30% to 65% as a thermal comfort zone. The minimum ventilation rate (ach) as recommended by ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 62.1, (2004) is 0.35 and that of openable area for natural ventilation in an office space is 4% of the net occupiable floor area (ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 62.1, 2016). For daylighting, the Architectural Energy Corporation, AEC (2006) put forward a DA threshold of 60% of the work plane illuminance (500lux in the case of offices); UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀ threshold of 80% of occupancy hours; sDA threshold of 75% (AEC, 2013).

Table 2. Simulation Results for the current conditions of ABU Senate building, Zaria

ABU SENATE BUILDING							
DA= 52%, cDA = 0.73, UDI= 75%							
<i>It is a</i>							
Latitude and longitude	11°09'03.11"N / 7°39'20.32"E, 11°09'01.98"N / 7°39'21.21"E, 11°09'02.95"N / 7°39'22.33"E, 11°09'03.96"N / 7°39'21.41"E						
		1 st floor	3 rd floor	4 th floor	5 th floor	6 th floor	8 th floor
		Academic office	Computer Room	Head Bursary Filing Room	Record Office	Secretary to Human Resource	Office/ Store
		NW	NW & NE	SW	NE	SW	NE
	Window to wall ratio	12.7%	27.5%	6.8%	9%	2.4%	10.7%
Daylight	DA (500)	30%	58%	46%	37%	35%	43%
	cDA (500)	0.48	0.64	0.68	0.54	0.53	0.58
	UDI (100-3000)	57%	55%	74%	57%	57%	57%
	sDA (8AM-5PM)	63%	97%	73%	77%	78%	90%
Thermal Comfort	Operative Temperature	24.3 ⁰ C-29.3 ⁰ C is in: May, June.	24.3 ⁰ C-29.3 ⁰ C is in: May, June	4.3 ⁰ C-29.3 ⁰ C is in: May, June	24.3 ⁰ C-29.3 ⁰ C is in: June, July, Aug., Sept., Oct.	24.3 ⁰ C-29.3 ⁰ C is in: June, July, Aug., Sept., Oct.	24.3 ⁰ C-29.3 ⁰ C is in: June
	Relative Humidity	30-65% is in: march, April.	30-65% is in: march, April.	30-65% is in: march, April.	30-65% is in: march, April, may, October	30-65% is in: march, April, may	30-65% is in: march, April, may

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IAQ	Ventilation rate (ach)	0.32	0.24	0.24	0.24	0.24	0.5
	Openable Window to floor area ratio	6.7%	6.4%	7.1%	2.7%	6.5%	3%

Source: field work, 2018

Table 3. Simulation Results for the current conditions of Nagwamatse house, Kaduna

NAGWAMATSE HOUSE KADUNA								
DA= 46%, cDA = 0.71, UDI= 73%								
Latitude and longitude	10°31'55.94"N / 7°25'42.97"E, 10°31'55.42"N / 7°25'43.01"E, 10°31'55.421"N / 7°25'43.19"E, 10°31'54.46"N / 7°25'43.31"E, 10°31'54.47"N / 7°25'43.83"E, 10°31'55.91"N / 7°25'43.64"E							
		1 st floor	2 nd floor	3 rd floor	4 th floor	5 th floor	6 th floor	8 th floor
		MD's office	Estate surveyor	AA Usman & CO	Mother care Office	Drawing office	KD Consult	Accounting Office
		E	W	E	E	E	E	W
	Window to wall ratio	10%	11.8%	10.6%	11.8%	5%	10.8%	7.2%
Daylight	DA (500)	43%	44%	41%	44%	25%	43%	44%
	cDA (500)	0.58	0.58	0.56	0.58	0.44	0.57	0.66
	UDI (100-3000)	55%	55%	54%	55%	56%	54%	74%
	sDA (8AM-5PM)	91%	86%	84%	92%	59%	89%	66%
Thermal Comfort	Operative Temperature	24.3°C-29.3°C is in: Mach, April	24.3°C-29.3°C is in: June, Aug., Sept., Oct., Nov.	24.3°C-29.3°C is in: July, Sept	24.3°C-29.3°C is in: Aug., Oct.	24.3°C-29.3°C is in: Aug., Oct.	24.3°C-29.3°C is in: April, Aug., Oct.	24.3°C-29.3°C is in: April, Aug., Oct.
	Relative Humidity	30-65% is in: May, June, Oct.	30-65% is in: June, Oct.	30-65% is in: May, June, Oct.	30-65% is in: May, June, Oct.	30-65% is in: June, Oct.	30-65% is in: May, June, Oct.	30-65% is in: May, June, Oct.
IAQ	Ventilation rate (ach)	0.158	0.16	0.158	0.158	0.31	0.155	0.43
	Openable Window to floor area ratio	3.5%	12%	5.5%	8.9%	3.5%	3.3%	8.88%

Source: field work, 2018

The research was analysed based on the research questions raised earlier in this paper. The first question is that:

- i. What is the level of compliance in daylighting requirements of mid-rise office buildings in Nigeria in fulfilling the DA, UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀ and sDA performance metrics put forward by AEC and SLL?

In this part, descriptive analysis was used to explore the level of compliance in daylighting requirements of ABU senate building and Nagwamatse house based on AEC and SLL.

From table 2 and 3, it could be observed that, none of the 13 offices has complied with 60% DA, or 80% UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀ requirements as specified in AEC (2013) and SLL, (2011) as shown in figure 3 and 4.

Figure 3. Comparison of Daylight Autonomy of the 13 offices in tropical wet and dry climate of Nigeria. Source: Field work, 2018

Figure 4. Comparison of Useful Daylight Autonomy of the 13 offices in tropical wet and dry climate of Nigeria. Source: Field work, 2018

The offices in ABU senate buildings have higher DA and UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀ values than those in Nagwamatse house, due to the effects of building form (ABU's is Eccentrically located service

core while Nagwamatse is centrally located core). It will be noticed that, Computer Room which is on the 3rd floor of ABU senate building, has 2 sources of daylight and has the highest WWR of 27.5%, consequently has the highest DA value, as seen in figure 5.

Figure 5. Daylight sensor illuminance Of computer room of ABU Zaria and Daylight sensor illuminance of Academic office ABU Zaria
Source: field work, 2018

It can also be observed that, *Office/Store* on the 8th floor of ABU senate building, with WWR greater than that of *Record office* on the 5th floor, has higher DA value than *Record office*, though they have the same orientation. While *Head Bursary Filing Room* on the 4th floor, with lower WWR than *Office/Store* on the 8th floor of ABU senate building, has higher DA value. *Accounting office* on the 8th floor of Nagwamatse house, oriented in west direction, and *Head Bursary Filing Room* on the 4th floor of ABU senate building with orientation of South-west, have the highest DA and $UDI_{100-3000}$. These show that Orientation, WWR, and building heights have influence on the value of DA and $UDI_{100-3000}$, on the mid-rise buildings.

It can also be seen from table 2 and 3 that, 4 offices out of 6 selected from ABU senate building and 5 out of 7 offices from Nagwamatse house, have more than 75% spatial daylight autonomy sDA, which means that, 9 offices in the two mid-rise buildings receive enough daylight during standard operating hours (8am to 5pm) as shown in figure 6. The figure also shows that,

Figure 6. Comparison of Spatial Daylight Autonomy of the 13 offices in tropical wet and dry climate of Nigeria. Source: Field work, 2018

Offices in Nagwamatse house have higher sDA values than those in ABU senate building, this is due to the effects of orientation and WWR. Offices in Nagwamatse house are either facing east or west, and those that have met the standard have WWR equal or greater than 10. Those two offices that have not meet the 75% requirement is due to their low WWR values as seen on table 3. When sDA, and $UDI_{100-3000}$ are considered together, it means that, those 9 offices receive more than the required daylight as they have not meet the required useful daylight illuminance, and therefore will produce unwanted heat and glare in those offices.

The next reserch question is:

- ii. To what extend does the operative temperature and relative humidity comply with ANSI/ASHRAE standard 55, (2017)?

It will be noticed from table 2 and 3 that, there is no office that meets ANSI/ASHRAE standard 55, (2017) criteria throughout the seasons. It can also be observed that, the number of months that optimum operative temperature and optimum relative humidity in offices are achieved depends on 5 factors, which are: orientation, Window to wall ratio of about 10; Openable Window to floor area ratio; building height; and type of roofing materials.

Offices that have windows facing South-west and West are more likely to achieve optimum operative temperature than others, followed by those facing North-East. For example, Estate Surveyors' office on 2nd floor of Nagwamatse house, has 5 months of optimum operative

temperature due to its orientation, WWR, roofing materials, and openable window to floor area ratio. Even though Office/ Store is on the 8th floor of ABU senate building, has WWR of 10.7% and enjoys North-East orientation, its optimum operative temperature is only in June due to its roofing material as well as its Openable Window to floor area ratio. The number of months that optimum operative temperature is achieved are more in offices of ABU senate building than in Nagwamatse house as seen in figure 7.

Figure 7. Duration of optimum operative temperature of the 13 offices in tropical wet and dry climate of Nigeria, relative to ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 55, (2017)
Source: Field work, 2018

It can be observed from table 2 and 3 that, optimum relative humidity also depends on those 5 factors earlier mentioned in this section, only that offices with windows facing North-East and East are more likely to achieve optimum relative humidity when other 4 factors are considered together. For example, even though Record office (on the 5th floor of ABU senate building) has low openable window to floor area ratio of 2.7, it has 4 months optimum relative humidity due to its orientation, WWR, relative position, and roofing materials, as seen in figure 8 below.

Figure 8. Duration of optimum relative humidity of the 13 offices in tropical wet and dry climate of Nigeria, relative to ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 55, (2017)

Source: Field work, 2018

The next question is that:

- iii. To what extent does ventilation rate comply with ANSI/ASHRAE standard 62.1, (2004; 2016)?

From table 2 and 3, it can be observed that, 5 out of 13 offices have not comply with 4% minimum openable area of the net occupiable floor area, for them to be naturally ventilated (ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 62.1, 2004). Moreover, only 2 offices comply with 0.35ach ANSI/ASHRAE standard 62.1, (2016) which are both on the 8th floor of Nagwamatse house and ABU senate building. ABU senate building has higher ach values than Nagwamatse due to its geometry, as seen on figure 9 below.

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Figure 9. Comparison of ventilation rate (ach) of the 13 offices in tropical wet and dry climate of Nigeria, relative to ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 90.1, (2004)
Source: Field work, 2018

Further studies will reveal the effects of openable window to floor area ratio; orientation, WWR, and building height on the ventilation rate in an office building.

CONCLUSION

This research has shown that, none of the IEC indicators (daylight autonomy, useful daylight illuminance, spatial daylight autonomy, operative temperature, relative humidity and air changes per hour) meet the standard's thresholds of IEC requirements as specified by AEC (2006), SLL (2011) and ANSI/ASHRAE standards. It has also been observed that, building form, room orientation, WWR, openable window to floor area ratio, building heights and roofing materials, influence the daylight and thermal comfort of an office building. However, 61.5% of the offices in the two buildings have met the standard threshold of 4% openable window to floor area ratio, and also 15% have met the minimum threshold of 0.35ach in ABU senate building and Nagwamatse house as required by AEC, SLL and ANSI/ASHRAE standards.

In conclusion, for mid rise buildings in tropical wet and dry climate of Nigeria to meet the IEC requirements based on the international standards, there is need to look at their building forms, orientations, WWR, roofing materials, and openable window to floor area ratios.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study has revealed the state of IEC in mid-rise office buildings in tropical wet and dry climate of Nigeria, using Nagwamatse house and ABU Senate building as case study. It has also revealed that, building form, orientation, WWR, openable window to floor area ratio, building heights and roofing materials, are major determinants of passive IEC in midrise office buildings. But how influential is each of these determinants? The significance of each of these determinants in relation to each other would be assessed using inferential statistic in further studies.

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